

RESEARCH PAPER

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTS OF WOMEN FARMERS' INVOLVEMENT IN COOPERATIVES ACTIVITIES ON THEIR ACCESS TO FERTILIZER.

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the effects of women farmers' involvement in cooperative activities on their access to fertilizer in Ondo State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study are to ascertain the impact of cooperatives on access to fertilizer and examine the constraints to cooperative activities carried out by women farmers. The list of women farmer cooperative members was collected from the local government area. Simple random sampling was used to select fifty respondents and structure questionnaire was used to elicit information from them. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency tables and percentages while regression analysis was used to ascertain the variables that affect access of women farmers to fertilizer. The findings shows that majority (82%) of the respondents had access to formal education, 76% had annual income with a maximum of N200,000.00, 52% are married and 64% have a family size of 4 at the minimum. The regression result analysis revealed that variables like types of fertilizer used, bags of fertilizer applied per annum are significant determinants of access to fertilizer, thus, they are variables that have tremendous implication for access to fertilizer. It was therefore recommended that the government should put in place a policy that will liberalize access to fertilizer for the respondents.

KEYWORDS: Effects, Women Farmers, Involvement, Cooperatives, Access and Fertilizer

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INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is of paramount importance to the nation's economy. It is the pivot of development in any nation like Nigeria which is blessed with suitable climate. About 80% of the Nigeria rural and urban population is engaged in agricultural related activities (Ani, 2002). It has in the past played a dominant role in the economy of the country. Women farmer in Nigeria form an active and reserve labour force but they rarely own the means of production (Rahman, 2004).

Women farmer participate in almost all aspect of agricultural production in Nigeria. There is abundant evidence that African women have been the principal producers of food crop right from the colonial age. However, the position of women in meeting challenges of agricultural development cannot be over emphasized. Women make a significant contribution to food production; they provide 60-80% of food production and assistance to their husband (Mgbada, 2002; Rahman, 2004). It has been observed that women work all the year round, while men engage in activities like clearing of bush seasonally. Women discovered agriculture in the Neolithic revolution, owing to their ancient role as gatherers of vegetable foods.

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Women supply most of the agricultural activities and this is the most important factor of production to farmers, as it is needed at all the stages of agricultural production, inadequate supply or unavailability of labour at any agricultural production stage can lead to unexpected shortage. This important factor are been greatly supplied by women as family labour in Africa. (Satio, 1992) reported that the Africa is the region of women's involvement in agricultural production in this area.

Considering these immense contribution of women in agriculture it is therefore of vital importance to address issues that may constrain them in agricultural production. Institutions are frequently cited as a major constraint to development, particularly for agriculture that involves many small farmers including women (Idachaba, 1989). Empirical studies have shown that the deprivation women face in terms of agricultural production resource access is influenced by the socioeconomic characteristics of women. These socioeconomic characters include women's level of education and credit access (Okunade, 2007), access to extension information and cooperatives (Ogato *et al.*, 2009), farming experience, and decision making powers (Damisa and Yohanna, 2007)). The study of Ogato (2009) found that socioeconomic factors of respondents in that study affected women's ability to access resources.

In spite of these problems, large quantity of food is still expected from the rural areas to feed the growing urban and rural population. The feeding of the entire nation is essentially dependent upon the subsistence production capacity by women (Ayieko, 1996). While no grand design to meet this challenge is available, each nation tries to evolve its own strategy for increasing farm-level production is the formation and use of cooperatives particularly among women farmers who are in the majority both in population and active agricultural labour force in Africa (Idachaba, 1989). The emphasis on women emerged from the fact that they work on the farm all the year round producing food crops, growing at least 50% of the world food and up to 90% of rural food supply (Mgbada, 2002).

Apart from agricultural production, women's role in the national economy has long been realized. Any food production programme therefore, must pay particular attention to the organization and development of productive women cooperatives (Ayieko, 1996). The major advantage this confers on women is to enable them pool their resources and benefit optimally from economy of size and scale in their production process. Mutual aid is one of the laws of life while conscious cooperation with one's friends and neighbours is one of the necessary experiences in sustaining personality status.

Informal types of cooperative are as old as human history. Whenever people come together voluntarily to help one another by providing a group service, they actually have a simple form of cooperation. Cooperatives approach has therefore being suggested many times as an effective means of alleviating most of the problems of Nigerian agricultural development. This is because it involves the pooling together of individual resources for common goal.

Some of the functions of cooperative approach as enumerated by Osuntogun (1986). These include;

- (a) Provision of modern storage facilities
- (b) Purchase and acquisition of farm inputs at reasonable price.
- (c) Achieving greater efficiency in both production and marketing of produce
- (d) Providing extension services and educating members' unimproved techniques of production.

The agricultural services of women go beyond crop production to other agricultural aspects like poultry and livestock production. In most cases, women do not only assist their husbands on their farms but also own farms themselves. A survey report in the pastoral northern region of the Sudan confirmed that women sometimes cut down forests, clear the bush or shrub, weed, drive away birds, harvest and winnow the crops. They sell the bulk of both cash and food crops, process dura (sorghum), millet, siasm (sesame), groundnuts and vegetables. The aims of the study were to analyze the effects of women farmers' involvement in cooperative activities on their access to fertilizer and examine the constraints to cooperative activities carried out by women farmers in Ondo State, Nigeria.

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METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Akure North Local Government Area of Ondo State. Her geographical location falls within the tropical rainforest area of about 300mm-350mm rainfall per annum with good rate of sunshine. Majority of the farmers produces agricultural products such as yam, cassava, maize, sweet potatoes pepper, okra, cocoyam and some cash crops.

A list of women farmers who are cooperatives members was collected from the Local Government Area and simple random sampling was used to select fifty respondents.

Data were collected from the respondents through the use of structured questionnaire. The questionnaire elicited information on demographic and non-demographic variables. The demographic variables consisted of age, sex, family size, marital status, level of education among others. The non-demographic variables were sources of finance, size of their farm, problem involve in sourcing for finance and many more.

The data collected from the survey were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis such as frequency tables and percentage distribution. Also, regression analysis was used to measure the effects of women farmers' involvement in cooperatives activities on their access to fertilizer and ascertain the Socio-economic variables that will significantly affect their access to fertilizer.

Regression analysis was used to determine the effect of specified independent variables on the access to credit. The linear regression model is as specified below:

- $Y = F(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6, \dots, e_i)$
Y = Access to fertilizer
X₁ = Type of fertilizer normally use
X₂ = Years of fertilizer application
X₃ = Quantity of fertilizer apply per annum
X₄ = Years of farming
X₅ = Farm size
X₆ = Age of the farmers
E_i = Error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study showed that 52% of the respondents were married and this may imply their farming vocation could generate enough income for them to sustain their respective families. Majority (64%) of the respondents had a family size of four (4) at the minimum. This could imply that family members will serve as a source of labour in their farming activities.

Majority (82%) of the respondents had formal education and this may imply that the respondents may understand the importance of cooperative society and thus participate effectively in their activities. Besides, they easily adopt innovation. Also, 76% of the respondents had an annual income with a maximum of two hundred thousand naira. This may indicate that their scale of operation and farm size are small.

Most (54%) of the respondents had access to farm land either through lease, Inheritance or purchase. This may have implications on the type of investment on the land in the study area.

On fertilizer usage, 42% of the respondents used all kinds of fertilizer. This may be as a result of their experience in fertilizer usage as 56% of them had maximum of 10 years experience. This may imply that they are exposed enough to know when and how to use different types of fertilizer in the study area.

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Majority (82%) of the respondents claimed to have their source of fertilizer from the government. This may be an indication that government distributes fertilizer to farmers in the study area. 72% used maximum of 6 bags per annum. This reflects that the scale of their operation to be small. Most (44%) of the respondents claimed to encounter the problem of high cost of purchasing fertilizer with other levels of challenges like inadequate credit (20%), transportation (80%) and scarcity of the input (22%).

Table 1: Personal Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Marital status		
Single	14	28.0
Married	26	52.0
Divorced	6	12.0
Widowed	4	8.0
Total	50	100.0
Family size		
1 – 3	18	36.0
4 – 7	20	40.0
8 – 10	8	16.0
Above 10	4	8.0
Total	50	100.0
Educational level		
No formal education	9	18.0
Adult education	6	12.0
Primary education	5	10.0
Secondary education	10	20.0
Tertiary education	20	40.0
Total	50	100.0
Experience of fertilizer usage		
2 – 5	20	40.0
6 – 10	20	40.0
11 - 16	4	8.0
17 – 25	4	8.0
Above 25	2	4.0
Total	50	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2010.

Table 2: Annual Income

Amount	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Less than ₦50,000.	7	14.0
₦50,000. – ₦100,00.	18	36.0
₦101,000. – ₦200,000.	8	16.0
₦151,000. – ₦200,000.	5	10.0
Above ₦200,000.	12	24.0
Total	50	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2010.

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Table 3: Method of Land Acquisition

Method of Acquisition	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Inheritance	23	46.0
Lease	12	24.0
Gift	4	8.0
Purchase	11	22.0
Total	50	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2010

Table 4 Fertilizer Usage

Fertilizer	Frequency	Percentages (%)
NPK 15:15:15:	14	28.0
Urea	6	12.0
Measure	9	18.0
All kinds	21	42.0
Total	50	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2010.

Table 5: Source of Fertilizer

Source	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Factory	3	6.0
Extension Agent	6	12.0
Government	41	82.0
Total	50	100.0

Source: : Field survey, 2010

Table 6: Quantity of Fertilizer Applied per Annum

Bags of fertilizer	Frequency	Percentages (%)
1 – 2	8	16.0
2 – 3	11	22.0
4 – 6	17	34.0
Above 6	14	28.0
Total	50	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2010.

Table 7: Problems Encountered in Fertilizer Application

Problems	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Inadequate Credit	10	20.0
Transportation	4	8.0
Scarcity	11	22.0
High cost of purchase	22	44.0
Others	3	6.0
Total	50	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2010.

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Determinants of Access to Fertilizer

To estimate the coefficient of the determinants of access to fertilizer, linear regression analysis was used. Based on the results, the regression equation is as depicted below;

$$Y = 1.463 + 0.43X_1 + 0.37X_2 + 0.612X_3 - 0.108X_4 + 0.089X_5 - 0.007X_6$$

(0.065) (0.009) (0.351) (0.048) (0.071) (0.068) (0.092)

$$R^2 = 0.852, \quad R^2 = 0.831, \quad F = 41.238$$

- Value is significant at 5% level.

Figure in percentages are standard errors.

The R^2 which is the Co-efficient of multiple determination is 0.852. This implies that 85.2% of the variability in access to fertilizer is accounted for by the specified independent variables. Independent variables like type of fertilizer used (X_1) and bags of fertilizer applied per annum (X_3) were significant at 5% level. This may imply that X_1 and X_3 are important variables that can affect the access of the women farmers to fertilizer in the study area. The positive signs associated with fertilizer usage (X_2), quantity of fertilizer used (X_3) and farm size (X_5) implies that the magnitude of these variables the better the access while conversely the negative signs associated with years of farming (X_4) and age of farmers (X_6) implies that the higher the magnitude of these variables the lower the access. The results obtained further indicated that all the explanatory variables entered in the model with expected signs, thus confirming to a *priori* expectation.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it was found that the respondents used different types of fertilizer and they mainly used a maximum of six bags per annum implying that they produce in small scale. Major constraints to access to fertilizer are high cost of purchase and inadequate access to credit.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on these findings, the following recommendations were made;

- Government should be able to supply adequate fertilizer and other productive inputs to women farmers in order to carry out their farming operation.
- Government should subsidize the price of fertilizer.
- Government should ensure there is availability of loan to women farmers so as increase their production
- The cooperative societies of the women farmers can help in purchasing productive inputs including fertilizer in bulk so that members can get them at affordable prices.

REFERENCES

- Ani A.O (2002): Factors inhabiting Agricultural production among rural Women in southern Ebonyi, State, Nigeria, Unpublished Phd Thesis University of Maiduguri, Nigeria.
- Ayieko A.C. (1996): Women in the Twentieth Century World, John Wiley and Sons New York, USA.
- Damisa, M. A. and Yohanna, M. (2007): Role of rural women in farm management decision making process: Ordered Probit Analysis. *World Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 2007, 3, No. 4, 543 – 546.
- Idachaba, K.C. (1989): An impact study on the adoption of improved agricultural technology by groundnut farmers in Hawal L.G.A of Borno State, Nigeria. *Nigerian J. Rural Dev. Coops.* Pp 7:19-25
- Mgbada, J.U. (2002): Production of staple crops by Rural Women in Enugu and Ebonyi, State Lesions for Enhancing poverty Alleviation Programmes. In Olowu T.A. (Editor) Agricultural Extension Society of Nigeria Pp 10-12.

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Ogato, G.S., Boon, E.K. and Subramani, J. (2009): Improving Access to Productive Resources and Agricultural Services through Gender Empowerment: A case study of three rural communities in Ambo district, Ethiopia. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 2009. 27, No.2, 85 – 100.

Okunade, E. O. (2007): Accessibility of Agricultural Credit and Inputs to Women Farmers of Isoya Rural Development Project. *Research Journal of Agricultural and Biological Sciences*, 2007, 3, No.3. 138 – 142.

Rahman S.A. (2004): Gender differential in Labour contribution and productivity in farm production Empirical Evidence from Kaduna State of Nigeria. Paper presented at the National Conference on Family held at new theatre complex Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria 1st – 5th March.

Saito, K. (1992): Raising the productivity of women farmers in sub-sarhara Africa overview Report Vol. 1 Washington, Population and Human Resources Development World Bank.

